

A REAL-TIME AXBT DATA ACQUISITION AND PROCESSING SYSTEM USING A
PERSONAL COMPUTER

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Abstract

At the Naval Research Laboratory Airborne-launched Expendable Bathythermographs (AXBT's) which are also known as Bathysonobuoy's are deployed from Anti-Submarine Warfare (ASW) aircraft in support of Naval oceanographic experiments. A highly portable real-time data acquisition and processing system has been developed on a Hewlett Packard HP150 Personal Computer for use aboard a P3 ASW aircraft to acquire, process, display and produce a hard copy graph of vertical ocean temperature and sound velocity profiles. The use of Personal Computers to acquire and process oceanographic data in real-time has significantly reduced the weight and power requirements aboard the aircraft while increasing the data acquisition system reliability. The hardware costs are very low in comparison with previously used mini-computer systems and a backup system is easily provided. Installation time and problems are minimized with the use of the small portable Personal Computers. This paper describes the design and implementation of the system as well as a detailed description of the software and system operation.

I. Introduction

In order to determine the structure of the ocean for Naval operational purposes the vertical temperature variations of the ocean must be known. This information is used to calculate the speed of sound in the ocean for underwater acoustic models and studies, to locate oceanographic fronts and eddy's and to characterize the ocean.

The aircraft is an excellent oceanographic platform for studying the temperature variations in the ocean since it is highly mobile so that it can be on-station quickly, and it can survey large areas in a short period of time. The AXBT's are often deployed from aircraft in support of other scientific studies when ocean temperature is an important parameter. The aircraft is weight, space, and power limited, so highly portable and lightweight real-time data acquisition and processing systems are desirable and often necessary.

In 1980 a portable system for acquiring and processing AXBT's was developed using intelligent computer terminals (1). The system worked well and was used when space, power and weight had to be minimized on the aircraft. Otherwise, the standard AXBT data acquisition and processing system developed on a Hewlett Packard HP1000 was used (2). There are certain drawbacks with the intelligent terminal data acquisition system such as: the digital data acquired from the bathythermograph recorder has a digital resolution of one-half degree Fahrenheit (F), whereas the probe has a resolution of 0.018 degrees F; the software had to be developed in assembly language making modifications time consuming and difficult; and one terminal was configured for real-time data acquisition and a second terminal for processing, display and hard copy output.

Putting the AXBT data acquisition and processing system on a Personal Computer was a natural extension of the work done on the intelligent terminal. At the time of the intelligent terminal development the hardware and software commercial tools did not exist on the personal computers. Today the control of instruments and the transfer of data on Personal Computers are handled by using standard hardware interfaces such as the IEEE-488 or RS-232 which are found on both the instrument and on the Personnel Computer. In order to control and receive data from these instruments the Personal Computer manufacturers have provided higher level software such as BASIC and FORTRAN making the programming as compared to assembly language relatively fast and easy.

II. Description of AXBT Instrumentation

The AXBT instrumentation used on Navy P3 Anti-Submarine Warfare (ASW) aircraft consists of an AN/SSQ-36 Bathythermobuoy that is deployed from the aircraft, an AN/ARR-52 or equivalent Radio Receiver, and an R0-308/SSQ-36 Bathythermograph Data Recorder.

The AN/SSQ-36 AXBT has been designed to measure water temperature in the ocean. The bathythermobuoy is considered a special sonobuoy and it has two working depths, 304.8 and 609.6 meters. The Bathythermobuoy is deployed from an aircraft and uses a parachute to retard descent. The impact of the water initiates the jettison of various components no longer required and starts

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the sequence of events that activate the AXBT. When the parachute is released a floating antenna is erected and at the same time sea water activates the battery which powers the electronics. A bomb like sinking thermistor temperature probe with a wire attached is released from near the surface and descends to the bottom of the ocean. The maximum measurement depth is determined by the length of the wire (304.8 or 609.6 meters). When the probe reaches this depth the wire breaks and further information can no longer be transmitted to the aircraft.

The depth of the thermistor probe is determined from its descent rate which is 1.52 meters per second which has an accuracy of 4.6 meters or 2 percent of depth whichever is greater. The probe produces an electrical signal which frequency modulates the AXBT transmitter. The signal frequency is then proportional to the water temperature which is received by the aircraft.

The AN/ARR-52 Radio Receiver aboard the P3 ASW aircraft receives the transmitted signal on one of three independent receiver channels. The radio receiver amplifies and demodulates the r-f signals for up to three AXBT's transmitting at three different carrier frequencies. This permits multiple sonobuoys to be active at the same time without frequency ambiguity occurring. The frequency of the transmission is linearly proportional to the temperature which can be derived by measuring the frequency and using the formula:

$$f = 20 T + 800 \quad (1)$$

where: f is the frequency in Hz
T is the Temperature in degrees Fahrenheit

or

$$f = 1440 + 36 t \quad (2)$$

where: t is the temperature in degrees Centigrade.

To complete the temperature data acquisition and processing aboard the aircraft a RO-308/SSQ-36 Bathythermograph data recorder is used. The frequency information from the receiver is converted to a digital eight bit number representing degrees Fahrenheit with the least significant bit equal to one-half degree. The analog signal is also used to drive a small x-y recorder to show temperature versus depth graphically. This digital signal was used by the intelligent terminal data acquisition system described above to record temperature variations in the ocean.

In order to improve the resolution of the data the RO-308/SSQ-36 Bathythermograph data recorder was not used in the development of the data acquisition and processing system on the Personal Computer. The demodulated frequency output of the AN/ARR-52 Radio Receiver was used directly. The signal was fed to a commercially available Hewlett Packard HP5345A Electronic Counter with a

standard digital IEEE-488 General Purpose Interface Bus (GPIB). The Personal Computer acquired the AXBT data over this interface which was used to calculate and then plot temperature versus depth.

III. Description of AXBT Data Acquisition and Processing System Hardware

The major hardware components of the AXBT data acquisition and processing system consist of the AN/SSQ-36 AXBT, the AN/ARR-52 Radio Receiver, the Hewlett Packard HP5345A Electronic Counter, and the HP150 Personal Computer. Figure (1) is diagram of the AXBT real-time data acquisition system.

Figure 1. Diagram of the AXBT Real-time Data Acquisition and Processing System.

The AN/SSQ-36 AXBT is manufactured by several vendors and has different configurations. It is deployed as a cylinder through a sonobuoy chute in the aft center portion of the P3 ASW aircraft. The frequency to digital converter (FDC) or HP5345A Electronic Counter was selected since it has all of the salient features required and it is programmable remotely through the GPIB. The HP150 Personal Computer has available from Hewlett Packard an HP-IB Command Library of software routines that can be used with a higher level programming language such as BASIC. The Library provides an Input/Output software driver to external devices such as the HP5345A. GPIB software libraries are available from Hewlett Packard and National Instruments (the software is called Lab Boss) for IBM PC/AT personal computers. A photograph of the AXBT Real-time Data Acquisition and Processing System aboard a P3 ASW aircraft is shown in Figure (2).

IV. AXBT Data Acquisition and Processing Software System Description

The data acquisition and processing software was developed directly on the HP150 Personal Computer using the Microsoft GWBASIC interpreter and an HP-IB Command Library developed by Hewlett Packard. The software was made highly modular for ease of development and testing. The software was broken

Figure 2. Photograph of the AXBT Personal Computer Data Acquisition and Processing System Aboard the P3 ASW Aircraft.

up into seven modules, namely: Main, Input/Output Driver, Initialization, Frequency Counter, AXBT Signal Detection, Data Acquisition, and Data Storage. Each of the modules will be described separately below.

1. Main

The Main program calls the other modules (subroutines) in their respective order.

2. Input/Output (I/O) Driver

The Input/Output driver was developed by Hewlett Packard and utilizes the the HP-IB Command Library (3). The driver has been designed to be general purpose and it supports the IEEE-488 GPIB. Hewlett Packard provides a program called SETUP.BAS which contains the necessary calls to the command routines to accomplish the I/O over the bus. This routine is merged into the BASIC program and occupies the first 999 statement numbers. The user program begins at statement 1000. In order to use the HP-IB Library routines the environment variable "PCIB" is assigned to the library directory. This is accomplished by changing statement 100 in SETUP.BAS.

Below is a list of steps required to use the HP-IB Command Library in a BASIC program.

a. Copy the library under MS-DOS to the GWBASIC disc and call it "A:\LIB"

b. LOAD "BASIC"

c. LOAD "A:\LIB\SETUP.BAS"

d. Use the editing features to assign PCIB to the Library directory by changing statement 100.

```
100 PCIB.DIR$= "A:\LIB"
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e. Store the modified program by SAVE "SETUP.BAS."

f. Load the BASIC program then load SETUP.BAS. Save the program under a new name and the I/O driver is merged into the BASIC program.

3. Initialization

The initialization module begins by developing a question and answer session with the operator. The intent of this module is to fully document the AXBT measurement by placing the information into a file header. The information required is the AXBT number, AXBT file name, time of day, positional coordinates where the AXBT was deployed from the aircraft, and a guess as to the water surface temperature using historical information. The surface water temperature guess is used by the detection module.

4. Electronic Counter

The HP5345A Electronic Counter is set by the program to the desired range by using a set of commands through the General Purpose Interface Bus.

5. AXBT Detection

As described above, shortly after the AXBT enters the ocean a radio receiver antenna is deployed and the radio transmitter is activated. The transmitter begins sending signals to the receiver for approximately two minutes before the AXBT probe begins its descent to the bottom of the ocean. From prior operations it has been found that noisy signals often approximate the surface temperature frequency which results in false data acquisition starts. To avoid these false starts a detection algorithm is employed. The algorithm calculates a window of plus and minus five degrees of the expected water surface temperature. All initial readings that fall outside this window are discarded. When a value falls within the window the time is stored and data acquisition begins.

6. Data Acquisition

Following the detection of an AXBT signal the program timer is turned on and readings are taken at one second intervals. The readings are stored in a buffer behind the header information. Three hundred data values (approximately 5 minutes) are stored for each AXBT. The value of temperature is printed on the CRT as it is acquired in order to

monitor the reasonableness of the data. Approximately ten percent of the AXBT's never transmit data due to equipment problems. If the AXBT is inoperable the run is terminated and a decision is made to deploy another.

7. Data Storage

Following the acquisition of 300 data points the file is transferred from the memory buffer to a floppy disc file for retention and future processing and analysis. Future processing generally consists of editing erroneous points, conversion of temperature versus depth to sound velocity versus depth and matching results with historical data. Both temperature and sound velocity versus depth are plotted on a Hewlett Packard Thinkjet Printer in an offline mode.

V. AXBT Plotting Software

During the data acquisition and processing mode the temperature versus depth information received from the AXBT is recorded on a file in a floppy disc. This data can now be used in an offline mode for display, editing and to obtain hard copy output. The end result is a plot of the Sound Velocity Profile for that geographical location.

Before plotting the data it is checked for erroneous values using an editor or word processor. The erroneous data are easy to detect since the points generally create large discontinuities in the data and then return to a continuous pattern. The discontinuities are generally removed by interpolation or smoothing since the data is slowly changing. In the past these errors were automatically detected using a statistical algorithm and smoothed by fitting the remaining data.

Once having removed erroneous points a temperature versus depth plot of the data is made and then compared with historical data. This temperature versus depth data is used for ocean micro-structure research studies. For underwater acoustical studies the sound velocity profile is computed based upon the temperature, pressure (depth) and salinity of the water. A plot of sound velocity at this geographical location is made and the sound velocity data is then transferred for use in ocean acoustic models.

The graphics instructions provided by GWBASIC were used to develop the plotting software. The program begins by requesting the operator enter the file name. The operator does so and the program draws the grids, labels the plot and draws the data. GWBASIC does not contain graphic lettering instructions so a subroutine is used that will draw alphanumeric in the graphics mode. A hard copy is obtained by sending the graphics screen to the Hewlett Packard Thinkjet printer. Figure (3) is a copy of a typical AXBT temperature versus depth plot with uncorrected data.

A description of the editing and plotting programs are provided below.

1. EDITPLOT

Unwanted radio noise that occurs during data transmission between the AXBT and the radio receiver is often within the bandwidth of the receiver and produces erroneous data. This erroneous data are easily recognizable since they appear as spikes or step functions which is seen when the data is plotted.

Program EDITPLOT provides the tools necessary to perform this editing in the shortest possible time. The program is loaded under BASIC. The raw data disc is placed in disc drive B and the corrected data disc placed in disc drive A. A temperature versus depth plot is generated on the display. An editing menu is provided so the analyst can quickly remove erroneous points. These points are replaced by smoothing the data. Following the editing procedure a new plot of temperature versus depth is generated. The procedure can be repeated until the analyst is satisfied that erroneous data have been removed. Figure (3) shows a temperature versus depth plot of raw data and Figure (4) a plot after the data has been smoothed using EDITPLOT.

Figure 3. Plot of Temperature versus Depth Uncorrected Data.

2. PLOT150

A plot of temperature versus depth is performed by using this program. A hard copy of the plot can be obtained by selecting an operator option to direct the plot to the hard copy device.

3. PSV150

The velocity of sound in the ocean is a critical parameter when performing underwater acoustical studies. The velocity is a function of temperature, pressure (depth), and salinity. The AXBT provides the temperature and pressure information and salinity must be obtained by sampling or using historical data. Plot Sound Velocity (PSV150) uses the mathematical model

Figure 4. Plot of Temperature versus Depth with Smoothed Data.

found in Reference (4). The program works in the same manner as PLOT150. Figure (5) is a plot of sound velocity versus depth generated by this program using the HP150 and Thinkjet printer.

4. MULTIPLT

MULTIPLT produces a composite plot of data files stored on the disc identified in the directory file called FNS (File NameS). Figure (6) is a composite plot of Sound Velocity versus Depth produced by program MULTIPLT.

5. PPSVBAT

Since plotting can be a time consuming task the program Plot and Plot Sound Velocities in BATCH (PPSVBAT) has been written to queue the data files in a directory and plot them serially in a "batch" mode.

VI. Data transfer from HP150 to mini-computer

In order to transfer the data from files stored on the HP150 floppy disc to a mini-computer for use by computer models a program developed by Hewlett Packard called ADVANCELINK was used (5).

VII. Conclusion

This real-time data acquisition system demonstrated that for slowly varying data Personal Computers can adequately perform the data acquisition, processing and analysis of the oceanographic data. The advantages of using the Personal Computers are low cost, easy interfacing and programming, low power consumption, portability, reliability and their general flexibility. In fact the report delineating the results of a recent study was prepared on the same Personal Computer that was used in the aircraft and this paper was written on that computer. NRL has gone one step further with the use of personal computers and has used an IBM PC/AT for high speed

Figure 5. Plot of Sound Velocity versus Depth.

Figure 6. Composite Plot of Sound Velocity versus Depth.

data acquisition and processing for four channels of underwater acoustic data at a bandwidth of 8 KHz using the Interactive Laboratory System (ILS) software from Signal Technology Incorporated (6). A description of this work will be published by the principal investigator.

VIII. Future Program Developments

The geographical position of the temperature probe is extremely important when using the temperature information gathered by the AXBT in underwater acoustic models and ocean finestructure studies. It is essentially a problem of registering the data. The automatic logging of navigational data can be achieved by using the digital positional information that is available from the Litton LTN-72 Inertial Navigation System used by the aircraft and crew for position keeping and

navigation. The computational power of the HP150's 8 MegaHz Intel 8088 microprocessor is sufficient to keep up with the data acquisition requirements if processing and I/O routines are coded in assembly language. It is expected that this major enhancement will be done in the near future to assist the experimenters in collecting and processing their data.

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